

Fine Structure of the Atomic Hydrogen Spectrum in the Lobachevsky Space

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Solutions of the radial Dirac equation for a particle with spin $1/2$ moving in the Coulomb field in the Lobachevsky space are presented in the form of power series. The three-term recurrence relations for the coefficients of the series are obtained and used to derive the expansions in inverse powers of the radius of curvature for the energy levels of bound states of the particle.

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1. Introduction

Quantum mechanical models based on the geometry of a curved space have been applied for the description of various phenomena in condensed matter (see e.g. [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]). It is often important to have a solvable model with a sufficient number of parameters. Such properties have some models in which an external field is combined with the curved space background. In particular, this applies to the problem of the hydrogen atom in spaces of a constant curvature. This problem was first solved on the base of nonrelativistic wave equation by Schrödinger [6] for the space of a constant positive curvature and by Infeld and Schild [7] for the space of a negative curvature. The use of the solutions of the Dirac equation in curved spaces would extend the scope and capacities of the geometric models. However, no analytic solutions are known to the radial Dirac equations with the Coulomb potential in spaces of a constant curvature. The existing

treatments [8, 9] of the Dirac – Coulomb problem in these spaces are of perturbative character. We take here a somewhat different approach which is based on the solution of the radial Dirac equation in the form of power series.

2. Radial equations for a particle with spin $1/2$ in the Lobachevsky space

We start with the formulation of the Dirac equation for a particle with spin $1/2$ in the space-time with metrics

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - dl^2, \quad (1)$$

where dl^2 is the metrics of the three-dimensional Lobachevsky space. We write here dl^2 in conformal coordinates,

$$dl^2 = \frac{1}{\phi^2} [(dx^1)^2 + (dx^2)^2 + (dx^3)^2],$$
$$\phi = 1 - \frac{r^2}{4\rho^2}, \quad r^2 = (x^1)^2 + (x^2)^2 + (x^3)^2, \quad (2)$$
$$0 \leq r < 2\rho,$$

where ρ is the curvature radius of the space.

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The generally covariant Dirac equation is ($\hbar = c = 1$)

$$\left[i\gamma^k h_{(k)}^\mu (\partial_\mu + \Gamma_\mu) - m \right] \Psi = 0, \quad (3)$$

where

$$\Gamma_\mu = \frac{1}{2} S^{mn} h_{(m)}^\nu \nabla_\mu h_{(n)\nu}, \quad S^{mn} = \frac{1}{4} (\gamma^m \gamma^n - \gamma^n \gamma^m),$$

and Dirac matrices γ^m ($m = 0, 1, 2, 3$) obey the relations

$$\gamma^m \gamma^n + \gamma^n \gamma^m = \eta^{mn} = \text{diag}(1, -1, -1, -1).$$

Taking nonzero components of orthotetrads $h_{(m)}^\nu$ as

$$h_{(0)}^0 = 1, \quad h_{(1)}^1 = h_{(2)}^2 = h_{(3)}^3 = \phi,$$

we get from (3) Dirac equation for a free particle in the metrics (1) in the form [10]

$$\left[i\gamma^0 \partial_0 + i\phi \hat{\partial}_x + \frac{i\hat{x}}{2\rho^2} - m \right] \Psi = 0, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\hat{\partial}_x = \gamma^1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x^1} + \gamma^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x^2} + \gamma^3 \frac{\partial}{\partial x^3},$$

$$\hat{x} = \gamma^1 x^1 + \gamma^2 x^2 + \gamma^3 x^3.$$

Introducing the interaction with an external electric field $U = U(r)$ and taking the time dependence of the wave function Ψ in the form $\Psi = \psi e^{-iEt}$ we rewrite the equation (4) as

$$\left[i\gamma^0 \left(\phi \hat{\partial}_x + \frac{\hat{x}}{2\rho^2} \right) - m\gamma^0 + E - U \right] \psi. \quad (5)$$

We write the matrices γ as

$$\gamma^0 = \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & -I \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma^\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_\alpha \\ -\sigma_\alpha & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \alpha = 1, 2, 3,$$

where σ_α are the Pauli matrices, and I is a unit 2×2 matrix. Setting

$$(x^1, x^2, x^3) = (r \sin \theta \cos \varphi, r \sin \theta \sin \varphi, r \cos \theta),$$

we write the wave function ψ in the form

$$\psi = \frac{\phi}{r} \begin{pmatrix} f(r) \Omega_{JM}^L(\theta, \varphi) \\ ig(r) \Omega_{JM}^{L'}(\theta, \varphi) \end{pmatrix}, \quad L' = 2J - L, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\Omega_{JM}^{J+1/2}(\theta, \varphi)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} -\sqrt{\frac{J-M+1}{2(J+1)}} Y_{J+1/2, M-1/2}(\theta, \varphi) \\ \sqrt{\frac{J+M+1}{2(J+1)}} Y_{J+1/2, M+1/2}(\theta, \varphi) \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$\Omega_{JM}^{J-1/2}(\theta, \varphi) = \begin{pmatrix} -\sqrt{\frac{J+M}{2j}} Y_{J-1/2, M-1/2}(\theta, \varphi) \\ \sqrt{\frac{J-m}{2J}} Y_{J-1/2, M+1/2}(\theta, \varphi) \end{pmatrix}$$

are spherical spinors, and $Y_{J\pm 1/2, M\pm 1/2}(\theta, \varphi)$ are spherical harmonics [11].

After the separation of variables, we arrive at the equations

$$\begin{aligned} \phi \left[f'(r) + \frac{\kappa}{r} f(r) \right] - (E + m - U) g(r) &= 0, \\ \phi \left[g'(r) - \frac{\kappa}{r} g(r) \right] + (E - m - U) f(r) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where κ is a nonzero integer [11]. By setting

$$r = 2\rho \tanh \frac{\beta}{2}, \quad 0 \leq \beta < \infty,$$

and taking the Coulomb potential U in the form

$$U = -\frac{\alpha}{\rho} \coth \beta, \quad (8)$$

we rewrite equations (7) in a more familiar form (cf. [8, 9])

$$\begin{aligned} f'(\beta) + \frac{\kappa f(\beta)}{\sinh \beta} - [(E + m)\rho + \alpha \coth \beta] g(\beta) &= 0, \\ g'(\beta) - \frac{\kappa g(\beta)}{\sinh \beta} + [(E - m)\rho + \alpha \coth \beta] f(\beta) &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Note that the potential (8) differs from the one used in [7] by a constant α/ρ .

Putting $x = 1 - e^{-\beta}$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$, we come

to the system of equations with four regular and two apparent singularities

$$\begin{aligned} (x-1)f'(x) - \frac{2\kappa(x-1)}{x(x-2)}f(x) - \frac{\alpha(x^2-2x+2) - (E+m)\rho x(x-2)}{x(x-2)}g(x) &= 0, \\ (x-1)g'(x) + \frac{2\kappa(x-1)}{x(x-2)}g(x) + \frac{\alpha(x^2-2x+2) - (E-m)\rho x(x-2)}{x(x-2)}f(x) &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

By making a substitution

$$f(x) = -\sqrt{(m+E)\rho - \alpha} (F_1 - F_2), \quad g(x) = \sqrt{(m-E)\rho + \alpha} (F_1 + F_2), \tag{11}$$

we eliminate one apparent singularity and come to equations

$$\begin{aligned} (x-1)F_1' - \frac{b^2x(x-2) + 2\alpha(E\rho - \alpha)}{x(x-2)}F_1 + \frac{2[b\kappa(x-1) + \alpha m\rho]}{bx(x-2)}F_2 &= 0, \\ (x-1)F_2' + \frac{b^2x(x-2) + 2\alpha(E\rho - \alpha)}{x(x-2)}F_2 + \frac{2[b\kappa(x-1) - \alpha m\rho]}{bx(x-2)}F_1 &= 0, \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where $b = \sqrt{m^2 - (E\rho - \alpha)^2}$.

By eliminating F_2 , we obtain for F_1 the second order equation

$$\begin{aligned} F_1'' + \left[\frac{b\kappa}{\alpha m\rho + b\kappa(x-1)} + \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x-1} + \frac{1}{x-2} \right] F_1' + \frac{1}{x(x-1)(x-2)} \left[-\frac{2b_0^2}{x} - \frac{2b_0^2}{x-2} + \frac{b_1^2}{x-1} \right. \\ \left. - b(b-1)(x-1) - \frac{\alpha m\rho}{\kappa} - \frac{\kappa^2(m^2 - E^2)\rho^2 + \alpha^2(\kappa^2 - m^2\rho^2)}{\kappa(\alpha m\rho + b\kappa(x-1))} \right] F_1 &= 0, \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where $b_0 = \sqrt{\kappa^2 - \alpha^2}$, $b_1 = \sqrt{m^2 - (E\rho + \alpha)^2}$.

3. Solutions of the wave equation and the energy spectrum

Taking into account the behavior of solutions of equation (13) at the singularities, we write the solution of this equation in the form

$$F_1 = x^{b_0}(x-1)^{b_1}(x-2)^{b_0} \sum_{k=-n_r-1}^{\infty} d_k x^{n_r+k+1}, \tag{14}$$

where an integer n_r is used to enumerate the solutions. On substituting solution (14) into

equation (13), we obtain the four-term recurrence relations

$$A_k d_{k+2} + B_k d_{k+1} + C_k d_k + D_k d_{k-1} = 0, \tag{15}$$

where

$$A_k = 2(2b_0 + n_k + 2)(b\kappa - \alpha m\rho)(n_k + 2),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
B_k &= \alpha m \rho [(2b_0 + b_1 - b + n_k)(2b_0 + b_1 + b + n_k + 1) + (4b_0 + 2b_1 + 2n_k + 3)(n_k + 2)] \\
&+ \kappa \{b_1^3 + 2\alpha E \rho - b_1 [(2b_0 + b_1 + n_k + 1)(2b_0 + b_1 + 5n_k + 6) - b_1(2n_k + 1)] + 2(m^2 - E^2)\rho^2\}, \quad (16) \\
C_k &= 2b[b + (2b_0 + b_1 + n_k)(n_k - 1)] - (\alpha m \rho - 2b\kappa)(2b_0 + b_1 - b + n_k)(2b_0 + b_1 + b + n_k + 2),
\end{aligned}$$

$$D_k = -b\kappa(2b_0 + b_1 + b + n_k)(2b_0 - b + n_k - 1),$$

and $n_k = n_r + k$. Denoting the left-hand side expression in (15) by Z_k , we can ascertain that

$$Z_k = \frac{1}{\sigma_{k+1}} [-b\kappa Y_k + (b\kappa - \alpha m \rho) Y_{k+1}], \quad (17)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_k &= \alpha m \rho [\alpha m \rho (2b_0 + b_1 + b) \\
&+ (\alpha m \rho + b\kappa)n_k] - b\kappa^2 [(b_1 + b)^2 + 4\alpha^2]/2, \quad (18)
\end{aligned}$$

and Y_k is a three-term linear combination of coefficients d_k ,

$$Y_k = \alpha_k d_{k+1} + \beta_k d_k + \gamma_k d_{k-1}$$

with $\alpha_k, \beta_k, \gamma_k$ given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_k &= \frac{\sigma_k A_{k-1}}{b\kappa - \alpha m \rho}, \\
\beta_k &= \frac{(\alpha m \rho - b\kappa)\sigma_{k+2} D_{k+1} - b\kappa\sigma_{k+1} C_k}{b^2 \kappa^2}, \quad (19) \\
\gamma_k &= -\frac{\sigma_{k+1} D_k}{b\kappa}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus coefficients d_k obey the three-term recurrence relations

$$\alpha_k d_{k+1} + \beta_k d_k + \gamma_k d_{k-1} = 0, \quad (20)$$

where $\alpha_k, \beta_k, \gamma_k$ are defined by (19), (18) and (16).

Introducing the continued fractions

$$R_k = \frac{d_k}{d_{k-1}} = \frac{-\gamma_k}{\beta_k + \alpha_k R_{k+1}},$$

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$$L_k = \frac{d_k}{d_{k+1}} = \frac{-\alpha_k}{\beta_k + \gamma_k L_{k-1}},$$

one gets a transcendental equation

$$R_1 L_0 = 1. \quad (21)$$

Considering the behavior of $\alpha_k, \beta_k, \gamma_k$ for $k \rightarrow \infty$, we find that

$$\alpha_k/s_k \rightarrow 2, \quad \beta_k/s_k \rightarrow -3, \quad \gamma_k/s_k \rightarrow 1,$$

where $s_k = \alpha m \rho (b\kappa + \alpha m \rho) k^3$. Therefore we may conclude (see [12]) that

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d_k}{d_{k-1}} = \frac{1}{2},$$

if the transcendental equation (21) is satisfied, and this limit is equal to 1 otherwise. Thus series (14) converges for $0 \leq x \leq 1$, provided equation (21) is satisfied, and this equation can be used for calculation of discrete levels of energy. Generally, this equation can only be solved numerically. But in the recurrence relations (20) we have for large ρ

$$\frac{\alpha_k \gamma_k}{\beta_k^2} \sim \frac{1}{\rho^2},$$

if the Coulomb interaction constant $\alpha \neq 0$. Therefore we are able to obtain from equation (21) an expansion for energy levels in powers of $1/\rho$:

$$E = E(n_r, \kappa) = \frac{m\delta}{\Delta} + \frac{\kappa - 2\delta\Delta}{4m\rho^2} + \frac{1}{32\alpha^2 m^3 \rho^4} \{-6\alpha^2 n_r \Delta^3 - \kappa(10n_r^2 + 7\kappa^2 - 4\alpha^2 + 1)\Delta^2 + [2\alpha^2 n_r(n_r^2 - \kappa^2 + 4\alpha^2) - \kappa^2\delta(4\alpha^2 - 3)]\Delta + 5\kappa[4\alpha^2 n_r^2 + (n_r^2 - \kappa^2)^2]\} + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho^6}\right), \tag{22}$$

where $\delta = n_r + b_0 = n_r + \sqrt{\kappa^2 - \alpha^2}$ and $\Delta = \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \delta^2}$. The first term in the expansion (22) which has no dependence on the sign of κ can be rewritten as

$$E_0 = m \left[1 + \frac{\alpha^2}{(n_r + \sqrt{\kappa^2 - \alpha^2})^2} \right]^{-1/2}. \tag{23}$$

The expression for energy levels in flat space is usually written in this form. It is seen from (23) that n_r is the radial quantum number. The second term in (22) can be written as

$$E_2 = \frac{\kappa}{4m\rho^2} - \frac{(n_r + \sqrt{\kappa^2 - \alpha^2})^2 + \alpha^2}{2m\rho^2} \left[1 + \frac{\alpha^2}{(n_r + \sqrt{\kappa^2 - \alpha^2})^2} \right]^{-1/2}. \tag{24}$$

The expression (24) coincides with the one found in the paper [9]. It already shows the splitting of order $1/\rho^2$ of levels with $\kappa = |\kappa|$ and $\kappa = -|\kappa|$. From the equation (22) we find this splitting to be

$$\Delta E = E(n_r, |\kappa|) - E(n_r, -|\kappa|) = \frac{|\kappa|}{2m\rho^2} + \frac{|\kappa|\{\Delta^2(4\alpha^2 - 7\kappa^2 - 10n_r^2 - 1) + 5[(\kappa^2 - n_r^2)^2 + 4\alpha^2 n_r^2]\}}{16\alpha^2 m^3 \rho^4} + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho^6}\right). \tag{25}$$

The terms of higher orders in $1/\rho$ are rather cumbersome. We write here an expansion for energy of the ground state with $n_r = 0, \kappa = -1$ up to the term of order $1/\rho^6$

$$E(0, -1) = m\sqrt{1 - \alpha^2} - \frac{1 + 2\sqrt{1 - \alpha^2}}{4m\rho^2} + \frac{(3 - 4\alpha^2)(1 + \sqrt{1 - \alpha^2})}{32\alpha^2 m^3 \rho^4} - \frac{(1 + 4\alpha^2)[(-3 + 2\alpha^2)\sqrt{1 - \alpha^2} - 3 + 3\alpha^2]}{128\alpha^4 m^5 \rho^6} + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho^8}\right)$$

and an expression for splitting of levels with $n_r = 1$ and $\kappa = \pm 1$

$$\Delta E = E(1, 1) - E(1, -1) = \frac{1}{2m\rho^2} - \frac{(9 - 2\alpha^2)\sqrt{1 - \alpha^2} + 9 - 7\alpha^2}{4\alpha^2 m^3 \rho^4} - \frac{(204 - 27\alpha^2 - 44\alpha^4)\sqrt{1 - \alpha^2} + 204 - 129\alpha^2 - 57\alpha^4 + 12\alpha^6}{16\alpha^4 m^5 \rho^6} + O\left(\frac{1}{\rho^8}\right).$$

4. Conclusion

We have found solutions of the radial Dirac equation for a particle with spin 1/2 in the Coulomb field in the Lobachevsky space as a power series convergent in all the range of physical

variable. This enabled us to derive expansions in the inverse powers of the radius of curvature of the space for discrete energy levels. These expressions show some important features of interaction of spin with metrics, such as levels splitting.

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